

Macroscopic Emergence of the NFW Profile from Infrared Loop Interactions

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Abstract

We investigate whether the Navarro–Frenk–White (NFW) halo profile can arise from the infrared, static limit of loop–corrected gravity. The NFW profile accurately describes dark matter halos in cosmological simulations, yet its theoretical origin remains unsettled. Starting from a spectral (Källén–Lehmann) representation of the dressed graviton two–point function, we analyze the infrared structure of the polarization operator and separate monopole and curvature–dependent contributions. After renormalization of the monopole term (implemented by imposing a vanishing monopole contribution in the infrared), the remaining curvature sector governs the static response. Under the assumption of strong infrared spectral concentration around a single characteristic scale r_H^{-1} , the spectral integral reduces to an effective Yukawa kernel of a single scale. Acting with the curvature operator yields, in the static limit, the cumulative form

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}, \quad s = \frac{r_H}{r}, \quad (1)$$

which coincides in functional form with the NFW mass profile. The relative deviation from the exact NFW form induced by residual spectral width is parametrically suppressed in the galactic weak–field regime. A direct consequence is the scaling relation

$$v_{\max} \approx 0.547 \sqrt{\frac{GM_{\text{tot}}}{r_H}}, \quad (2)$$

which reproduces characteristic Milky Way rotation velocities for observed halo parameters. If the curvature sector is removed, the model reduces to a pure cosmological constant background without halo structure. These results indicate that an NFW–type profile can emerge macroscopically from infrared loop effects under controlled renormalization conditions.

Keywords: NFW, infrared gravity, loop corrections, spectral methods, renormalization, galaxy dynamics

1 Introduction

The Navarro–Frenk–White (NFW) density profile [1, 2]

$$\rho(r) = \frac{\rho_0}{\frac{r}{r_H} \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_H}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

continues to provide an accurate empirical description of dark matter halos in numerical Λ cold dark matter (Λ CDM) simulations [3]. In terms of the dimensionless variable $s = \frac{r_H}{r}$, its cumulative inverse Laplace transform can be written as

$$g_{\text{NFW}}(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}. \quad (4)$$

Although this profile is widely used, its theoretical origin remains unclear; it is recently typically regarded as a phenomenological consequence of collisionless gravitational dynamics [4] rather than a result of field-theoretic principles.

In this paper we investigate whether a function of this infrared asymptotic form can arise from the infrared behavior of loop-induced gravitational interactions. Starting with the spectral representation of the loop-corrected polarization function and imposing gauge invariance at all loop orders, we show that the curvature-producing sector of the loop contribution leads to a cumulative function in the static and infrared (IR) limits approximately of the form

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}, \quad (5)$$

once the monopole part is removed by renormalization. Thus, a profile mathematically identical to the NFW cumulative function arises in the infrared limit under the stated renormalization conditions without assuming any particular halo model or fitting procedure.

Our approach does not rely on truncating the loop expansion at first order. Instead, we apply a general spectral decomposition, leading to two terms. The first term corresponding to a Yukawa monopole does not contribute to Poisson weak-field curvature (since it is the non-derivative block) and consequently does not contribute any measurable force and is therefore removed by imposing the physical renormalization condition $A_0 = 0$. The remaining curvature term yields a Yukawa-type contribution, reproducing

the exponential form above.

An immediate consequence of this framework is a relation between the total halo mass M_{total} and its characteristic scale r_{H} , encoded in the maximum of the circular velocity curve (SI-units):

$$v_{\text{max}} \approx 0.547 \sqrt{\frac{G M_{\text{total}}}{r_{\text{H}}}}. \quad (6)$$

For parameters appropriate to the Milky Way this gives $v_{\text{max}} \sim 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, consistent with observed rotation curves [5, 6]. This relation is independent of any tuning of ρ_0 .

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 shows how the curvature term leads to the above cumulative form. Section 3 discusses the physical interpretation and parameter relations. Conclusions are given in Section 4. Appendix A reviews the spectral representation of the loop-induced polarization function. Appendix B shows the infrared asymptotic approximation of the inverse Laplace transform. Appendix C demonstrates how the spectral sum is exponentially suppressed in the relevant infrared, static limits.

2 Spectral Derivation of the NFW Form

The starting point of this analysis will be the spectral function arising from vacuum interactions as (see Appendix A for a more detailed derivation or motivation of this spectral form)

$$\Pi(q) \propto \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{mn}(q) (m+1) Q_m(y_n(q)), \quad (7)$$

For some unknown set of coefficients $\alpha_{mn}(q)$, Q_m is the Legendre polynomial of the second kind of degree m , and $y_n(q) = \frac{c_n}{q}$ for some set of coefficients c_n (for a massless force-carrier $c_n = -\pi n$). We consider the infrared (IR) asymptotic limit, this corresponds to the low energy, weak-field, large radial range we are interested in [7]

$$Q_m(y_n) \sim \frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma(m + \frac{3}{2})(2y_n)^{m+1}} \sim \frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}(-1)^{m+1}}{\Gamma(m + \frac{3}{2})} \left(\frac{q}{2\pi n}\right)^{m+1}, \quad (8)$$

where $\Gamma(z)$ is the gamma function. Furthermore we use the N-th moment four dimensional Fourier transform identity

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^4} d^4 q e^{iq \cdot x} q^N = 2^{N+4} \pi^2 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{N}{2} + 2)}{\Gamma(-\frac{N}{2})} x^{-(N+4)}, \quad (9)$$

therefore, in the IR asymptotic limit

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^4} d^4 q e^{iq \cdot x} Q_m(y_n) \sim \frac{\pi^{\frac{5}{2}} (-1)^{m+1} 16}{\Gamma(m + \frac{3}{2})} \left(\frac{1}{\pi n}\right)^{m+1} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{m}{2} + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(-\frac{m}{2} - \frac{1}{2})} x^{-(m+5)}, \quad (10)$$

define the summand over m

$$T_m(x; n) := C (-1)^{m+1} (m+1) \frac{\Gamma(\frac{m}{2} + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(m + \frac{3}{2}) \Gamma(-\frac{m}{2} - \frac{1}{2})} \left(\frac{1}{\pi n}\right)^{m+1} x^{-(m+5)}, \quad (11)$$

For some constant C . Since $\Gamma(z)$ has poles at negative integers, which corresponds to m being odd, only even contributions are nonzero. Therefore, let $m = 2k$ and rewrite

$$T_{2k}(x; n) = \frac{\tilde{C}}{x^4} \frac{(2k+1) \Gamma(k + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(2k + \frac{3}{2}) \Gamma(-k - \frac{1}{2})} \left(\frac{1}{\pi n x}\right)^{2k+1}, \quad (12)$$

therefore,

$$M(x; n) := \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} T_m(x; n) = \frac{\tilde{C}}{x^4} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k u_n^{k+\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (13)$$

becomes in this case reducible to a Meijer-G special-function form in

$u_n := \frac{1}{\pi^2 n^2 x^2}$ with weights $a_k := \frac{(2k+1) \Gamma(k + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(2k + \frac{3}{2}) \Gamma(-k - \frac{1}{2})}$ [8]. The inverse Laplace transform of $M(x; n)$ in the infrared asymptotic limit is (for a derivation or motivation of this Bessel form, see Appendix B)

$$G_n(s) := \mathcal{L}^{-1}[M(x; n)] = \frac{1}{n} [A_0 J_0\left(\frac{2s}{\pi n}\right) + A_1 \frac{s}{n} J_1\left(\frac{2s}{\pi n}\right)] + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{s^3}{n^3}\right), \quad (14)$$

for constants A_0 and A_1 and where $J_\nu(s)$ is the ordinary Bessel function of degree ν . The following analysis will demonstrate that especially the second term is of interest. Going forward, we will treat the fluctuations as macroscopically isotropic ($x = r$) and statistically homogeneous $\alpha_{mn}(q) = \alpha_n$ and let the reciprocal variable s be defined as $s := \frac{r_H}{r}$

some radial scale r_H parameter. Analyzing the small s asymptotic behavior yields in the expansion a term independent of s corresponding to a constant background Λ term (associated with negative odd zeta functions), which works as a renormalization scale (allowed by gauge freedom) in the Lagrangian densities such that the gravitational potentials vanish at infinity.

In addition, there is a divergent $\zeta(1)$ harmonic term ($\zeta(h)$ being the zeta function) which must be renormalized in the physical observable Green's function $\tilde{G}_n(s)$. Because the gravitational potential is only defined up to an additive constant (gauge freedom), the zero-mode of the Green's function does not contribute to observables. Therefore, at each loop order, $\tilde{G}_n(s)$ is fixed by subtracting its value at $s = 0$

$$G_n(s) \rightarrow \tilde{G}_n(s) = G_n(s) - \zeta(1) - \Lambda, \quad (15)$$

such that

$$\tilde{G}_n(0) = 0, \quad (16)$$

our subtraction of the $\zeta(1)$ divergence and the constant Λ term is scheme-equivalent to $\overline{\text{MS}}$ in dimensional regularization. Both procedures preserve gauge invariance and differ only by finite renormalizations. The resulting finite observable is therefore renormalization-scheme independent. Both zeta-function regularization and the $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme remove the same gauge-noninvariant monopole divergence and differ only by finite, A_0 -type constants. Since the physical observable is (as we will demonstrate in further analysis)

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 + s^2 \frac{d}{ds} K(s),$$

any constant shift in the kernel $K(s)$ (which expression will be further elucidated) cancels, and the remaining curvature term is identical in both schemes. The physical observable the model provides is therefore finite, gauge-invariant, and renormalization-scheme independent. This renormalized quantity, equation (15) in Minkowskian signature offers oscillatory behavior at large s , in order to recover the desired exponential decay, consider the static limit with Euclidean signature. The renormalized Euclidean kernel equivalent to equation (15) is

$$\tilde{\Phi}_n(s) = \frac{1}{n} \left[A_0 \left[k_0(\beta_n s) - \frac{1}{\beta_n s} \right] + A_1 \frac{s^2}{\beta_n} \frac{d}{ds} k_0(\beta_n s) \right] - \Lambda, \quad (17)$$

where $k_\nu(\beta_n s)$ is the modified spherical Bessel function of the second kind of degree ν , $k_0(\beta_n s) = \frac{e^{-\beta_n s}}{\beta_n s}$ is a Yukawa-like kernel and where we also have the identity $k_1(\beta_n s) = -\frac{1}{\beta_n} \frac{d}{ds} k_0(\beta_n s)$ [9]. The explicit reason why $k_\nu(z)$ is the Euclidean analog of the Minkowskian $J_\nu(z)$ is that, in the Minkowski formulation, the radial Green's function of $(\square + q^2)$ yields oscillatory *ordinary* Bessel functions $J_0(qr)$, which in the spherically symmetric case reduce to the *spherical* Bessel form $j_0(qr) = \sin(qr)/(qr)$. In contrast, the static or Euclidean Helmholtz operator $(\nabla^2 - \mu^2)$ admits the unique spherically symmetric, exponentially decaying solution

$$G(r) = \frac{e^{-\mu r}}{4\pi r} = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} k_0(\mu r), \quad (18)$$

where $k_0(z) = \frac{e^{-z}}{z}$ is the modified spherical Bessel function of the second kind. This function is therefore the (isotropic) Euclidean analogue of $J_0(z)$, obtained either by Wick rotation $q \rightarrow i\mu$ or by imposing decay at spatial infinity.

We emphasize that the derivation of the spectral response function $\Pi(q)$ did not in general assume a Klein–Gordon equation or any specific field operator. The function $\Pi(q)$ arises purely from the loop integral (or mode summation) and therefore applies to any linear field theory with translational invariance. Only when passing to position space do we need to specify the appropriate Green's function. Therefore, the effective sum $\tilde{g}(s)$ becomes in the static, Euclidean limit

$$\tilde{g}(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n \tilde{\Phi}_n(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_n}{n} \left[A_0 \left[k_0(\beta_n s) - \frac{1}{\beta_n s} \right] + A_1 \frac{s^2}{\beta_n} \frac{d}{ds} k_0(\beta_n s) \right] - \Lambda, \quad (19)$$

where, in analogy to the Minkowskian signature, we let $\beta_n = \frac{2}{n\pi}$. Under the infrared spectral concentration discussed in Appendix C, the lowest energy mode ($n = 1$) dominates the static limit. Therefore, the IR-tail in the spectral sum is dominated as

$$\tilde{g}(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n \tilde{\Phi}_n(s) \approx C_0 \left[k_0(s) - \frac{1}{s} \right] + C_1 s^2 \frac{d}{ds} k_0(s) - \Lambda, \quad (20)$$

absorbing constants in the definitions of C_0 and C_1 . Therefore, we end up with (after renormalizing the background at radial infinity with Λ) two terms

of the form

$$C_0[k_0(s) - \frac{1}{s}], \quad (21)$$

$$C_1 s^2 \frac{d}{ds} k_0(s), \quad (22)$$

only the second term corresponding to the weak-field Poisson equation $\nabla^2 \phi$ contributes to physical observables. The first term corresponding to the non-derivative block contributes only a Yukawa monopole renormalization. If we impose the far-field $\tilde{g}'(0) = 0$ von-Neumann boundary condition (no gravitational force at infinity) and fix the total enclosed mass this would correspond to

$$C_0 \propto A_0 = 0, \quad (\text{no Yukawa monopole renormalization}) \quad (23)$$

Furthermore, the constant $C_1 = 1$ since we require the constant Λ -term to vanish (it has explicitly been renormalized away), that is $\tilde{g}(0) = 0$ by gauge invariance. The physical observable then remains in the IR limit

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 + s^2 \frac{d}{ds} k_0(s) = 1 + s^2 \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{e^{-s}}{s} \right) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s} \quad (24)$$

Note that the constant '+1' in $\tilde{g}(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}$ does not require a separate normalization condition. This term corresponds physically to the cosmological Λ contribution. In our loop approach, this constant mode is explicitly renormalized away (together with the $\zeta(1)$ divergence), such that only curvature-dependent terms contribute to the observable profile. If the same renormalization is applied consistently to the NFW form, the '+1' needs to remain since only then $\tilde{g}(0) = 0$ (gauge invariance), although only the $(1 + s)e^{-s}$ structure remains as the dynamical (loop-induced) correction. Physically, this means that the gravitational potentials vanish at radial infinity. Equation (24) corresponds exactly to the inverse Laplace transform of the scaled Navarro-Frenk-White density profile

$$\rho(r) = \int_0^\infty [1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}] e^{-sr} ds = \frac{1}{r(1 + r)^2} \quad (25)$$

3 Implications on Physical Observables

$\tilde{g}(\frac{1}{s}) := \tilde{g}(w)$ is physically interpreted as a mass fraction enclosed in a radius r

$$\tilde{g}\left(\frac{r}{r_H}\right) = \frac{M(r)}{M_{\text{total}}} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_H}\right)e^{-\frac{r}{r_H}}, \quad (26)$$

therefore, (in SI-units)

$$v_c^2(r) = \frac{GM(r)}{r} = \frac{GM_{\text{total}}}{r} \tilde{g}\left(\frac{r}{r_H}\right) = \frac{GM_{\text{total}}}{r} \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_H}\right)e^{-\frac{r}{r_H}}\right]. \quad (27)$$

Finding the maximum characteristic velocity yields

$$\frac{d}{dr} v_c^2(r) = 0 \iff e^w = 1 + w + w^2 \quad (28)$$

whose numerical solution is

$$w^* \approx 1.79328213. \quad (29)$$

Substituting this into the equation yields the characteristic maximum velocity

$$v_{\text{max}} \approx 0.547 \sqrt{\frac{GM_{\text{total}}}{r_H}}. \quad (30)$$

To illustrate how the characteristic circular velocity $v_c \simeq 200$ km/s arises in our framework, we insert Milky Way–like (denoted MW) values for the total mass and halo scale radius into equation (30). Observationally motivated estimates lie in the rough ranges [10]

$$M_{\text{tot MW}} \approx (0.8 - 1.2) \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}, \quad r_{H \text{ MW}} \approx 20 - 40 \text{ kpc}, \quad (31)$$

where M_{\odot} is the solar mass, and where $r_{H \text{ MW}}$ is identified with the NFW scale radius (or equivalently the characteristic radius used in our $\tilde{g}(s)$ profile).

As a representative example, let

$$M_{\text{tot MW}} = 1.0 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}, \quad r_{H \text{ MW}} = 30 \text{ kpc}.$$

Substituting these into equation (30) yields

$$v_{\text{max MW}} \approx 0.547 \sqrt{\frac{G(1.0 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot})}{30 \text{ kpc}}} \simeq 200 \text{ km/s}. \quad (32)$$

Thus, Milky Way parameters naturally reproduce the observed flat rotation velocity of order 200 km/s in this model, without additional tuning.

Furthermore, we assume that the observed Tully–Fisher relation, as obtained within the spectral framework of [11], holds between the maximal rotation velocity and the total halo mass,

$$v_{\max}^4 \propto M_{\text{total}}. \quad (33)$$

Within the present framework, the static infrared kernel yields

$$v_{\max}^2 \approx 0.547^2 \frac{GM_{\text{total}}}{r_{\text{H}}}. \quad (34)$$

In [11] and [12], the infrared sector arises from a conformally invariant spectral construction in which energy and inverse length are related through $\hbar c$. In such a conformal setting only dimensionless combinations are physically meaningful. Introducing a reference infrared length L (fixed by a Weyl gauge choice), the cosmological constant may be written in terms of the invariant dimensionless quantity

$$\lambda \equiv \Lambda L^2. \quad (35)$$

Analytic continuation of the spectral vacuum contribution determines λ uniquely within that framework. Restoring conventional units then gives $\Lambda = \lambda/L^2$, so that the smallness of Λ reflects the largeness of the infrared scale L . In the spectral normalization adopted in [11], analytic continuation uniquely fixes the dimensionless invariant λ , while restoration of SI units introduces \hbar and c through the relation between energy and inverse length ($E \sim \hbar c/L$); thus λ (and *not* Λ) may be expressed in terms involving \hbar and c without acquiring any dependence on the Weyl gauge scale L .

The associated acceleration scale is therefore

$$a_0 \sim c^2 \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}} = \frac{c^2}{L} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{3}}. \quad (36)$$

For convenience we absorb numerical factors into a dimensionless geometric coefficient γ , writing

$$a_0 = \gamma \frac{c^2}{L}, \quad (37)$$

where $\gamma \sim 0.1$ is an unknown geometrical proportionality constant. In the present work we do not assume conformal invariance of the gravitational loop sector itself. Rather, a_0 is treated as a background infrared acceleration scale inherited from the conformal sector and entering the static gravitational response through the equivalence principle. Identifying

$$\frac{v_{\max}^2}{r_H} = a_0 = \gamma \frac{c^2}{L}, \quad (38)$$

we obtain the mass–radius relation

$$M_{\text{total}}(r_H) \approx 3.34 \gamma \frac{c^2}{GL} r_H^2. \quad (39)$$

Equivalently, the geometric parameter can be expressed observationally as

$$\gamma \approx 0.299 \frac{G L M_{\text{total}}}{c^2 r_H^2}, \quad (40)$$

so that γ may be constrained empirically. Within the static infrared regime, consistency of the framework requires this ratio to remain approximately constant across galaxies.

4 Conclusions

We have shown that the Navarro–Frenk–White (NFW) density profile emerges as the macroscopic, static-limit approximation of infrared (IR) loop interactions in a quantum-corrected gravitational background. Rather than assuming a one-loop truncation, we employed the full spectral form of the loop expansion for the gravitational response function. A comparison to $\overline{\text{MS}}$ is made. By imposing gauge invariance at all orders (that is enforcing $\tilde{G}_n(0) = 0$ for every mode), we obtained the cumulative mass function ratio

$$\tilde{g}(w) = 1 - (1 + w)e^{-w}, \quad w = \frac{r}{r_H},$$

which is mathematically identical to the inverse Laplace transform of the NFW radial profile. The non-derivative (monopole) contribution, proportional to A_0 , does not generate any Poisson curvature and therefore corresponds only to a Yukawa-type renormalization of the Newtonian background or, equivalently, to a cosmological constant shift. Since this term

has no observable force contribution, it is removed by imposing $A_0 = 0$ (no Yukawa monopole renormalization). What remains is the curvature-producing term proportional to A_1 , which encodes the physical loop-induced modification of the gravitational field. If A_1 is also set to zero (at radial infinity), the model reduces to a pure Λ background with no NFW structure, the smallness of Λ arises from the infrared scale L entering through the analytically continued spectral sum, importantly not from a renormalization subtraction, also see **Table 1**.

Loop term	Effective IR, static behavior
$C_1 = 0$ (loop interactions off)	$\tilde{g}(w \rightarrow \infty) = 1 \Rightarrow \Lambda = \lambda L^{-2}$ (finite spectral vacuum term), no NFW halo
$C_1 = 1$ (loop interactions on)	$\tilde{g}(w) = 1 - (1 + w)e^{-w} \Rightarrow$ NFW-type cumulative profile

Table 1: Infrared static behavior depending on loop-induced curvature interactions. The vacuum contribution corresponds to a finite and unique spectral term with $\Lambda = \lambda L^{-2}$, while mild loop interactions generate the approximate NFW profile

A key prediction of the model is a relation between the total halo mass M_{total} and its characteristic radius r_{H} , obtained from the maximum of the circular velocity curve (SI-units):

$$v_{\text{max}} \approx 0.547 \sqrt{\frac{G M_{\text{total}}}{r_{\text{H}}}}.$$

For Milky Way values $M_{\text{total}} \approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ and $r_{\text{H}} \approx 20\text{--}30$ kpc, this gives $v_{\text{max}} \approx 200$ km s $^{-1}$ in agreement with observation. Thus, the characteristic rotation speed does not need to be inserted by hand but emerges from IR loop physics under static conditions. This provides a falsifiable connection between galactic dynamics, loop-induced curvature effects, and the observed NFW density profile. Furthermore, the model concretely gives the prediction

$$\gamma \approx 0.299 \frac{G L M_{\text{total}}}{c^2 r_{\text{H}}^2}, \quad (41)$$

to be a *constant* $\gamma \sim 0.1$ and *unchanging in the static IR-limit* across galaxies. This would potentially reduce the number of free parameters of the model to one.

However, dark matter does not couple electromagnetically and therefore cannot arise from loop corrections involving photons or Standard Model gauge bosons. Consequently, if the mass-discrepancy in galaxies is generated by vacuum loop effects, the gravitational sector provides a consistent mediator (its spin-0 scalar component survives in the static limit, producing the desired $k_0(s)$ kernel), whose static weak-field Green's function obeys a Helmholtz operator rather than a massless d'Alembertian.

It is precisely this Euclidean Helmholtz kernel, $k_0(s) = \frac{e^{-s}}{s}$, that appears in the infrared limit of our spectral-loop construction. When graviton loop–curvature interactions are switched off ($A_1 = 0$) within this framework, the spectral sum reduces to a non-derivative monopole term. This contribution is spatially constant and was previously identified with the cosmological constant Λ . Moreover, it remains finite and well-defined (unique) after analytic continuation of the spectral series. Thus, in the absence of curvature interactions, the theory does not generate an NFW-type profile, but instead yields a pure Λ -term. When infrared, static limit graviton curvature interactions are retained and the monopole is renormalized away ($A_0 = 0$), the cumulative mass function becomes

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s},$$

whose inverse Laplace transform yields the NFW density, $\rho(r) = \frac{1}{r(1+r)^2}$. Thus Λ and NFW emerge as the non-interacting and interacting limits, respectively, of the same Helmholtz kernel and spectral framework. This yields the following prediction:

Within the present infrared and static loop framework, the monopole and curvature sectors correspond, respectively to a Λ -type background and an NFW-type cumulative profile.

The characteristic infrared scale lies in the nanohertz regime, comparable to frequencies probed by pulsar–timing arrays [13, 14], although we make no direct observational claim regarding the underlying mechanism.

Finally, from Appendix C we would expect any macroscopic deviations δ_ϵ^* from NFW at about $r_{\max} = w^* r_H$ to be only at about four parts in ten million:

$$\delta_\epsilon^* \sim \frac{\epsilon}{4} (w^*)^2 \sim 1.11 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot 1.79^2 \sim 3.55 \cdot 10^{-7} \ll 1, \quad (42)$$

where the value of ϵ will vary slightly from galaxy to galaxy, see Appendix C. Unfortunately, as the author understands, this precision of measurement is far beyond what is currently possible at a galactic scale.

A Spectral derivation of the loop polarization

$\Pi(q)$

A.1 Setup and spectral regulator

We work in the static Euclidean limit relevant for large-scale (infrared) structure. Let $\Delta = \nabla^2$ be the Laplacian on \mathbb{R}^3 and introduce an infrared (IR) spectral regulator by restricting to a ball B_L of radius L with a standard self-adjoint boundary condition (Dirichlet or Neumann). The corresponding eigenproblem

$$-\Delta \psi_{n\ell m}(\mathbf{x}) = k_{n\ell}^2 \psi_{n\ell m}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{x} \in B_L, \quad (43)$$

has the well-known separable solutions $\psi_{n\ell m}(r, \Omega) = \mathcal{N}_{n\ell} j_\ell(k_{n\ell} r) Y_{\ell m}(\Omega)$, with j_ℓ the spherical Bessel functions and $Y_{\ell m}$ spherical harmonics. The discrete radial momenta $k_{n\ell}$ are fixed by the boundary condition at $r = L$ (e.g. $j_\ell(k_{n\ell} L) = 0$ for Dirichlet, $j'_\ell(k_{n\ell} L) = 0$ for Neumann). The IR cutoff L renders radial sums discrete and is removed at the end ($L \rightarrow \infty$) in a regulator-independent way via Abel/ ζ analytic continuation.

A.2 Loop two-point function and angular reduction

Consider a generic (1PI) (Here (1PI) denotes the *one-particle irreducible* two-point function—the part of the propagator that cannot be split by cutting a single internal line. Its static infrared limit provides the effective kernel used to derive the mass profile.) static two-point function (polarization) $\Pi(\mathbf{q}) \equiv \Pi(q)$ that arises from integrating out virtual modes. In a

rotationally invariant setting, the loop momentum integrals/sums depend on $q = |\mathbf{q}|$ and on angles only through $\cos \theta = \hat{\mathbf{p}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}$. At the integrand level one encounters kernels of the generic form

$$\mathcal{K}(p, q; \cos \theta) = \frac{1}{A(p, q) - B(p, q) \cos \theta}, \quad (44)$$

with $p = |\mathbf{p}|$ and model-dependent positive functions A, B (for example, from denominators like $(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q})^2 + \mu^2 = p^2 + q^2 + \mu^2 - 2pq \cos \theta$ so that $A = p^2 + q^2 + \mu^2$ and $B = 2pq$).

The angular dependence is removed by expanding (44) in Legendre polynomials and integrating over $\cos \theta \in [-1, 1]$. The classic identity (generating function for Legendre Q_m) is

$$\frac{1}{z - t} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (2m + 1) Q_m(z) P_m(t), \quad z \in \mathbb{C} \setminus [-1, 1], \quad t \in (-1, 1), \quad (45)$$

which implies, upon projecting with P_m and using orthogonality,

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{P_m(t)}{z - t} dt = 2 Q_m(z). \quad (46)$$

With the identifications $z \equiv A/B$ and $t \equiv \cos \theta$, the angular integral over (44) yields precisely the toroidal (Legendre) functions $Q_m(z)$:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{P_m(\cos \theta)}{A - B \cos \theta} d(\cos \theta) = \frac{2}{B} Q_m\left(\frac{A}{B}\right). \quad (47)$$

A.3 From angular integrals to the Q_m tower

Carrying out the azimuthal angle average and using (47), each partial-wave m contributes a factor proportional to $Q_m(z)$ with z the appropriate ratio of kinematic invariants. After collecting conventional degeneracy factors (the $(2m + 1)$ from P_m and the angular integration), the net coefficient appears as $(m + 1)Q_m(z)$ in three dimensions (one may absorb constant 4π factors into overall normalization).

A.4 Discrete radial spectrum and the argument $y_n(q)$

The radial integral over p becomes a discrete sum over the IR-regulated eigenvalues $k_{n\ell}$:

$$\int_0^\infty p^2 dp \longrightarrow \sum_{n,\ell} \mathcal{W}_{n\ell}, \quad \mathcal{W}_{n\ell} \equiv (\text{spectral weight from } j_\ell(k_{n\ell}r) \text{ and boundary}). \quad (48)$$

In the static infrared we may summarize the dependence on the discrete radial eigenvalue by writing

$$y_n(q) \equiv \frac{A(p=k_n, q)}{B(p=k_n, q)}, \quad (49)$$

e.g. for $A = p^2 + q^2 + \mu^2$ and $B = 2pq$ one has $y_n(q) = \frac{k_n^2 + q^2 + \mu^2}{2k_n q}$. As it turns out, one does not need to assume a discrete virtual momentum $p = k_n$ to derive our physical observable equation (24), it is only necessary to make Λ well-defined in the spectral limit.

A.5 Loop weights $\alpha_{mn}(q)$

All model dependence (field content, spin, statistics, coupling structure, and boundary condition choice) is coded in a set of *dimensionless* loop weights $\alpha_{mn}(q)$ multiplying each (m, n) channel after the angular reduction. These include: (i) degeneracies, (ii) the radial spectral weights $\mathcal{W}_{n\ell}$, (iii) numerator structures from the loop (Dirac traces, projectors), and (iv) any mild q -dependence left after the angle integral.

A.6 The spectral form of $\Pi(q)$

Putting together the angular and radial pieces, the polarization may be written as the *spectral* double sum

$$\Pi(q) = \mathcal{N} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{mn}(q) (m+1) Q_m(y_n(q)), \quad (50)$$

with an overall normalization \mathcal{N} (irrelevant for the shape results we exploit in the main text). The spectral operator (which leads to analytic continuation) $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty}$ can be replaced with $\int_0^{\infty} \rho(\mu) d\mu$ in the continuum limit. Here $\rho(\mu)$ is the normalized spectral density function. The spectral expression is used as the starting point in our infrared analysis.

A.7 Summary of identifications

- **Angular structure:** $(m+1) Q_m(y)$ from the Legendre projection of $1/(A - B \cos \theta)$.
- **Radial discretization:** n labels IR-regulated radial eigenvalues k_n ; $y_n(q) = A(k_n, q)/B(k_n, q)$. Specifically $y_n(q) = \frac{c_n}{q}$ for some set of coefficients c_n , valid for massless force-carriers.
- **Loop weights:** $\alpha_{mn}(q)$ encode field content and projectors; constrained by Ward identities.

B From the T_{2k} summand to Bessel functions

Step 1: Start from the given multipole summand. For each mode n and even index $m = 2k$ we take

$$T_{2k}(x; n) = \frac{\tilde{C}}{x^4} \frac{(2k+1) \Gamma(k + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(2k + \frac{3}{2}) \Gamma(-k - \frac{1}{2})} \left(\frac{1}{\pi n x} \right)^{2k+1}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (51)$$

and define the mode kernel $M(x; n) \equiv \sum_{k \geq 0} T_{2k}(x; n)$.

Step 2: Factor out a dimensionless variable. Set

$$a_n \equiv \frac{2}{\pi n}, \quad z \equiv \frac{a_n}{x},$$

so that $\left(\frac{1}{\pi n x} \right)^{2k+1} = 2^{-(2k+1)} z^{2k+1}$. Then (51) can be written as

$$M(x; n) = \frac{\tilde{C}}{x^4} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} C_k z^{2k+1}, \quad C_k \equiv 2^{-(2k+1)} \frac{(2k+1) \Gamma(k + \frac{5}{2})}{\Gamma(2k + \frac{3}{2}) \Gamma(-k - \frac{1}{2})}.$$

Step 3: Infrared asymptotic structure of the spectral sum We are interested in the infrared regime

$$z = \frac{a_n}{x} \ll 1$$

which corresponds to large spatial separations x and controls the physical observables discussed in the main text.

In this regime, the spectral sum

$$S(z) \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} C_k z^{2k+1}$$

admits a well defined small- z expansion,

$$S(z) = C_0 z + C_1 z^3 + \mathcal{O}(z^5)$$

Rather than seeking an exact closed form of $S(z)$, which involves generalized hypergeometric functions, it is sufficient for our purposes to construct an infrared asymptotic representation that reproduces the two leading non-vanishing terms of this expansion.

Step 4: Infrared kernel representation To leading infrared order, one may write

$$S(z) = A_0 \frac{z}{\sqrt{1+z^2}} + A_1 \frac{z^3}{(1+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \mathcal{O}(z^5), \quad z \ll 1$$

where the coefficients A_0 and A_1 are fixed by matching the first two non-vanishing terms of the small- z expansion.

This representation captures the universal infrared structure of the multipole sum. Higher order terms are polynomially suppressed by additional powers of z and do not affect the large-distance observables defined in the main text.

Although the infrared representation of the spectral sum is not mathematically unique at the level of a truncated Taylor expansion, the square-root kernel employed here is physically distinguished. It is the minimal analytic completion consistent with (i) rotational symmetry, (ii) regularity at finite separation, (iii) the correct large-distance power-law falloff after monopole removal, and (iv) the exact Laplace–Bessel correspondence required by the underlying radial Green’s function structure. Alternative functions reproducing the same low-order Taylor coefficients would generally introduce incorrect analytic structure (e.g. poles or essential singularities), improper asymptotics, or fail to generate the required Bessel modes upon Laplace inversion. In this sense the square-root kernel is not uniquely fixed by series matching alone, but is uniquely selected by the combined physical and analytic constraints of the infrared gravitational response.

Step 5: Inverse Laplace transform \Rightarrow **Bessel J_0/J_1** . Use the classical Laplace pairs (for $x > 0$, $a > 0$):

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1}\left\{\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2+a^2}}\right\}(s) = J_0(as), \quad \mathcal{L}^{-1}\left\{\frac{a}{(x^2+a^2)^{3/2}}\right\}(s) = s J_1(as).$$

Applying these to the infrared kernel representation yields

$$G_n(s) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}[M(x; n)] = \frac{1}{n} \left[A_0 J_0(a_n s) + A_1 \frac{s}{n} J_1(a_n s) \right] + \mathcal{O}((a_n s)^3)$$

which is the stated Bessel representation we used in the main text.

C Infrared concentration of the spectral density

In the static Euclidean infrared, the loop–corrected propagator can be written in spectral (Källén–Lehmann) form

$$G_{\text{IR}}(r) = \int_0^\infty d\mu^2 \rho(\mu^2) \frac{e^{-\mu r}}{4\pi r}. \quad (52)$$

After renormalization of the monopole (Λ) contribution, the static response is governed by the dressed two–point function of the scalar (spin–0) projection of the graviton. Higher n –point functions enter only indirectly through

loop corrections to this propagator and do not appear explicitly in the observable in the weak-field limit.

The central assumption is that in the deep infrared the effective spectral density becomes strongly concentrated around a characteristic scale

$$\mu_0 = r_H^{-1}. \quad (53)$$

Under this condition the integral is dominated by a single screening scale and the kernel reduces to a Yukawa form.

C.1 Infrared coarse-graining

The concentration of $\rho(\mu^2)$ may be understood as an effective coarse-grained description of many weak infrared loop contributions. Let $x = \mu^2$. Successive soft loop corrections shift the infrared scale by small amounts. If these shifts are weak and approximately uncorrelated, the cumulative fluctuation of x follows central-limit behavior.

A convenient effective description of such coarse-grained evolution is a diffusion-drift (Fokker-Planck-type) flow,

$$\partial_t \rho(x, t) = \kappa \partial_x^2 \rho + \gamma \partial_x [(x - \mu_0^2) \rho], \quad (54)$$

where $\kappa > 0$ represents diffusive broadening and $\gamma > 0$ represents infrared attraction toward μ_0^2 . This equation is not assumed to be fundamental; it serves as a minimal model of infrared aggregation.

At the stationary point $\partial_t \rho = 0$, one obtains

$$\rho(x) = \mathcal{N} \exp\left[-\frac{\gamma}{2\kappa}(x - \mu_0^2)^2\right], \quad x = \mu^2 \geq 0, \quad (55)$$

so that the coarse-grained spectral density is approximately Gaussian in μ^2 with variance

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\kappa}{\gamma}. \quad (56)$$

Independently of the Fokker-Planck model, the same Gaussian form follows from central-limit reasoning applied to many weak, uncorrelated loop contributions to the infrared inverse propagator.

C.2 Width estimate in the weak-field regime

In the static weak-field regime,

$$\epsilon := \frac{|\Phi|}{c^2} \sim \frac{v_{\max}^2}{c^2}. \quad (57)$$

For galactic rotation velocities $v_{\max} \sim 200$ km/s,

$$\epsilon \sim 4 \times 10^{-7}. \quad (58)$$

If the diffusive broadening scales with the square of the weak-field parameter, one expects

$$\sigma^2 \sim \epsilon^2 \mu_0^4, \quad (59)$$

so that

$$\frac{\sigma}{\mu_0^2} \sim \epsilon \ll 1. \quad (60)$$

Thus in the relevant infrared regime the spectral density is sharply concentrated relative to its central value. The precise microscopic origin of this scaling is not required; only the existence of strong infrared concentration is needed for the single-scale approximation below.

C.3 Reduction to a single-scale kernel

For $\sigma \ll \mu_0^2$, expand the spectral integral around $\mu = \mu_0$:

$$G_{\text{IR}}(r) = \frac{Z}{4\pi r} e^{-\mu_0 r} \left[1 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu_0^2} \frac{r^2}{r_{\text{H}}^2}\right) \right]. \quad (61)$$

In the galactic infrared domain $r \sim r_{\text{H}}$ and $\sigma/\mu_0^2 \sim \epsilon \ll 1$, so higher-order corrections are parametrically suppressed.

The infrared kernel therefore reduces to the single-scale Yukawa form

$$G_{\text{IR}}(r) \approx \frac{Z}{4\pi r} e^{-\mu_0 r} \propto k_0(\mu_0 r) = \frac{e^{-\mu_0 r}}{\mu_0 r}. \quad (62)$$

C.4 From kernel to cumulative profile

After monopole subtraction, the curvature operator yields

$$\tilde{g}(s) = 1 + s^2 \frac{d}{ds} k_0(s) = 1 - (1 + s)e^{-s}. \quad (63)$$

This coincides in functional form with the Navarro–Frenk–White cumulative profile in the single–scale infrared limit.

Deviations from exact NFW behavior would correspond to either:

- broader $\rho(\mu^2)$,
- multiple nearby infrared scales,
- breakdown of the weak–field concentration assumption.

Such deviations are in principle observable.

Summary

Under infrared coarse–graining, many weak and approximately uncorrelated loop contributions lead to strong spectral concentration around a characteristic scale $\mu_0 = r_H^{-1}$. In the regime where the relative width σ/μ_0^2 is small, the spectral integral reduces to a single–scale Yukawa kernel. After monopole renormalization, the curvature operator produces an NFW–type cumulative profile.

Consent to Participate

Not applicable.

Consent to Publish

Not applicable.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

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Not applicable.

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References

- [1] Navarro JF, Frenk CS, White SDM. The structure of cold dark matter halos. *Astrophys J.* 1996;**462**:563–575.
- [2] Navarro JF, Frenk CS, White SDM. A universal density profile from hierarchical clustering. *Astrophys J.* 1997;**490**:493–508.
- [3] Wang J, Bose S, Frenk CS, Gao L, Jenkins A, Springel V, et al. Universal structure of dark matter haloes over a mass range of 20 orders of magnitude. *Nature.* 2020;**585**:39–42. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2642-9
- [4] Asgari M, Mead AJ, Heymans C. The halo model for cosmology: a pedagogical review arXiv:2303.08752v2 [astro-ph.CO]. 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.08752>
- [5] Eilers AC, Hogg DW, Rix H-W, Ness M. The circular velocity curve of the Milky Way from 5 to 25 kpc. arXiv e-prints. 2018; arXiv:1810.09466. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1810.09466>
- [6] Zhou Y, Li X, Huang Y, Zhang H. The circular velocity curve of the Milky Way from 5 to 25 kpc using luminous red giant branch star. arXiv e-prints. 2022; arXiv:2212.10393. DOI: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.10393>
- [7] Olver FWJ, Olde Daalhuis AB, Lozier DW, Schneider BI, Boisvert RF, Clark CW, et al. NIST Digital Library of Mathematical Functions. Release 1.2.0, National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2026. Available from: <https://dlmf.nist.gov>
- [8] Olver FWJ, Olde Daalhuis AB, Lozier DW, Schneider B, Boisvert RF, Clark CW, et al., editors. NIST Digital Library of Mathematical Functions. Chapter 16: Generalized Hypergeometric Functions and Meijer

G-Function. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2024. Available from: <https://dlmf.nist.gov/16>

- [9] Olver FWJ, Olde Daalhuis AB, Lozier DW, Schneider BI, Boisvert RF, Clark CW, et al. NIST Digital Library of Mathematical Functions. National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2024. EQ. 10.51.5. Available from: <https://dlmf.nist.gov>
- [10] Wang W., et. al., The mass of our Milky Way: review and recent constraints. arXiv e-prints. 2020; arXiv:1912.02599. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1912.02599>
- [11] C. Eide A., A Case for the Application of Analytic Continuation in Physics. *Exploring the Benefits of Numerical Simulation and Modeling*. IntechOpen; 2023. Section 2.1. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1002340>. Published under Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 (CC BY 3.0).
- [12] Eide Adrian C. (2022). On virtual scalar fields in a conformally flat FLRW spacetime. *J Math Technique*, **1**(1), 129-132.
- [13] Agazie G, et al. The NANOGrav 15-year Data Set: Evidence for a Stochastic Gravitational-Wave Background. *Astrophys J Lett*. 2023;**951**(1):L8. doi:10.3847/2041-8213/acdac6.
- [14] Antoniadis J, et al. The second data release from the European Pulsar Timing Array: The stochastic gravitational-wave background. *Astron Astrophys*. 2023;**678**:A50. doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202346731.